

Effectiveness of Teachers Training Programme at Elementary Stage: A Case Study on Teachers of Tinsukia District

Mrs. Rekha Moni Baruah

Associate Professor, Women's College, Tinsukia, Assam, India

ABSTRACT

The teacher is the most important factor in any educational program. He is the backbone of all educational institutions. To become a good teacher, he should have some qualities and to achieve these, professional training is must for every teacher.

So, the paper tries to study the overall impact of teacher training programme at elementary stage being organized under DIET and SSA in Tinsukia District, particularly in terms of implementation of new and innovative teaching techniques at classroom level by the teachers after getting trainings. There have been numbers of Teachers' Training Programme like in-service Teacher Training, Induction Training, Monthly Cluster and Zone Level Teacher Orientation Programme etc. being organized in all districts of Assam, mainly through District Institute of Education and Training (DIET) under SSA.

My study is confined to only 450 TET qualified teachers who are engaging in teacher training which are run by KKHSOU and other 50 teachers who have attended the short term courses of different subjects organized by SSA and DIET. The objective of the Researcher of the present study is to highlight the perception of trained teachers towards the training and effectiveness of teachers training programme at elementary level of Tinsukia District. So, I have visited the training centers and collected the information with face to face interview with the teachers and questionnaire to them and observed the environment of the centre. At last, some suggestions are also given for improvement and smooth functioning of training programme.

1. INTRODUCTION

Teacher is the backbone of all educational institution. He has the responsibility for the total development of a child and to prepare him as a citizen having good personality and moral values. To become a good teacher, professional training is compulsory for every teacher. In the present study, the investigator try to study the overall impact of teacher training programme at elementary stage being organized under DIET and SSA in Tinsukia District, particularly in terms of implementation of new and innovative teaching techniques at classroom level by the teachers after getting trainings.

There have been numbers of Teachers' Training Programme like in-service Teacher Training, Induction Training, Monthly Cluster and Zone Level Teacher Orientation Programme etc. being organized in all districts of Assam, mainly through District Institute of Education and Training (DIET) under SSA.

My study is confined to only 450 TET qualified teachers who are engaging in teacher training which are run by KKHSOU and other 50 teachers who have attended the short term courses of different subjects organized by SSA and DIET. The objective of the Researcher of the present study is to highlight the perception of trained teachers towards the training and effectiveness of teachers training programme at elementary level of Tinsukia District. So, I have visited the training centers and collected the information with face to

How to cite this paper: Mrs. Rekha Moni Baruah "Effectiveness of Teachers Training Programme at Elementary Stage: A Case Study on Teachers of Tinsukia District" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-4 | Issue-2, February 2020, pp.143-148, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd29923.pdf

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

face interview with the teachers and questionnaire to them and observed the environment of the centre.

2. Objective of the study

1. To study the perceptions of the trainees about the relevance and usefulness of teacher training programme.
2. To study the changes of teachers behaviour particularly in terms of implementation of new and innovative teaching techniques at classroom by the trainees after getting training.
3. To study the teachers perception about the syllabus, methods, training modules of teacher training program.
4. To analysis the opinion of different functionaries such as BRC/CRC, Co-coordinators on impact of teacher training programme.
5. To suggest measures for improving the future trainings to be imparted to teachers and ensuring greater utilization of training outcomes by teachers in classroom teaching.

3. Methodology

In the present study the researcher used the 'Descriptive Survey Method' which is based on literature, interview, and questionnaire & observation of the situation. The researcher interviewed with the District Project Officer of SSA, Tinsukia District and collected important data. A well structured questionnaire was prepared for the teachers of elementary

school who attended the different teacher’s training programme and tried to collect the information with face to face interview with trained teachers.

4. General Observation on Field Study

From my observation it is found that SSA, Tinsukia District has been trying its best to impart quality education in the primary stage by conducting various awareness and training programmes for the children as well as teachers. Various training programmes conducted by SSA in Tinsukia District are as follows:

- Teacher training programme on Right to free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009
- Monthly cluster and zone level teacher orientation programmes
- Teacher training on new text books (English/Mathematics/Science/Language etc.)

- Motivation Programmes for students and teachers to generate interest towards attending classes and schools
- Initiation of Action Research at school level
- School Block and Dist. Level Science/Maths Model cum project exhibition etc.

From the field study it is cleared that all teachers training programmes are organized on ‘cascade mode’. Trainings are first organised at the state level where are few Resource Persons (RPs) from each district receive training and then these RPs come back to their district and provide training to selected District Resource Persons(DRPs). Again these DRPs come back to their respective blocks/clusters and try to give training to teachers of different schools. All training programmes are cascaded to teachers at BRC level and CRC level by the resource persons of district level.

**ACTIVITIES OF SSA, TINSUKIA DISTRICT OF TEACHER TRAINING (2015-16)
In-service Training conducted during 2015-16**

TABLE :1

Sl no	Focus area	Target group	Duration	Physical target	achievement	% of achievement
1	Training on early grade reading writing and maths for class I & II	LP teachers	6 days	1204	1198	99.50
2	Monthly teacher orientation	LP & UP teachers	10 days, one day every month	4417	4308	97.53
3	Training on reading enhancement prog.	LP teachers	4 days	200	200	100
4	Training on language	LP teachers	2 days	20	20	100

SOURCE: SSA office, Tinsukia.

Six days block level training on early grade reading writing & maths: A Six days block level training on early grade reading writing & maths for class 1 & II teachers was conducted for 1204 no of teachers. The details breakup of teachers trained in 2015-16 academic year is as shown below:

TABLE:2

Block	Hapjan	kakapather	Margherita	sadiya	Tinsukia urban	Total
No of teacher trained	337	339	274	221	33	1204

SOURCE: SSA office, Tinsukia.

Monthly Cluster Level Teacher orientation:The cluster level monthly teacher orientation was conducted by SSA, Tinsukia district for 10 days to 4308 no of teachers.

Training on reading enhancement prog: 4 days training on reading enhancement prog. was conducted for 200 teachers by SSA, Tinsukia district.

Training on language: Two days district level training was conducted on Tea Garden community language where 20 no of teacher trained.

Training on untrained teacher: SSA has 282 physical target for TET qualified teacher to provide training for two year. Centre wise breakup of teacher deputed as shown below:

TABLE: 3

Sl no	Name of centre	No of trainee deputed	No of teachers trained
1	Doomdooma college	100	29
2	Tinsukia college	91	39
3	Margherita college	91	64
	total	282	132

SOURCE: SSA office, Tinsukia

Overall progress and targets for teachers training**TABLE : 4**

Type of training	Target for training in 2015-16	Achievement	% of achievement
	Phy	Phy	Phy
In- Service	4417	4308	97.53
Untrained teacher training	591	441	73.09

SOURCE: SSA office, Tinsukia

It has been found from my field study that now many teachers' training programme like in-service Teacher Training, Induction Training, Monthly Cluster and Zone Level Teacher Orientation Programme etc. are organized in the district mainly by District Institute of Education and Training (DIET) and SSA in collaboration with KKHSOU.

ACTIVITIES OF DIET, TINSUKIA DISTRICT ON TEACHER TRAINING (2010-16)

The teacher training programmes organized by DIET, Tinsukia from 2010 to 2016 are shown in the following table:

TABLE: 5

DIET, TINSUKIA			
Year	Name of the course	Total No. of Teachers	Duration
2010 - 11	D. EL. Ed	102 L P Teachers	2 Years course
		100 U P Teachers	2 Years course
2011 - 12	D. EL. Ed	102 L P Teachers	2 Years course
		100 U P Teachers	2 Years course
2012 - 13	D. EL. Ed	06 L P teachers	2 Years course
2013 - 14	D. EL. Ed	06 L P teachers	2 Years course
2015 - 16	Science Training	50 No. L P teachers	4 Days
2015 - 16	Maths Training	50 No. U P teachers	4 Days
2015 - 16	Blue Print Preparation and Question Paper Setting	100 No. L P teachers	5 Days
2015 - 16	Art and Education	100 No. L P teachers	5 Days

Source: DIET, Tinsukia.

From the above table it clears that from 2010-2016 DIET has organised nos. of training courses for quality development of the elementary stage.

5. The analysis and interpretation of data

To success in my study I have visited D.EL.ED teachers training centres of Tinsukia district which are conducted by KKHSOU collaboration with SSA and DIET, Tinsukia district. I have collected data with help of face to face interview with trainees, resource persons and co-ordinators of those centres and distributed the questionnaires to the trainees. I have also visited some primary schools and collected information from 50 teachers through the questionnaire methods who have attended short term/ B.ED training programme. Thus, I have observed the situation of schools and training centres as a whole and try to analysis the collected information with the following heads:

- Training needs.
- Training modules, syllabus & methods applied
- Physical facilities in the training centre and actual classroom
- Resource persons and coordinators.
- Strengths and weakness of training etc.

The Sample of the present study consists of 500 trained teachers of Tinsukia district. After completion my field works, I try to make a comparison among the objectives and field study. Thus, to meet the objectives of the present study I have collected information and gathered a lot of experiences from the field which are tried to discuss below.....

OBJECTIVE WISE ANALYSIS

OBJECTIVE: 1 The first objective of the present study was to find out the perceptions of the trainees about the relevance and usefulness of Teacher Training. To achieve this objective I collected primary data from the field and the collected data are tabulated in the following:

Teachers Attitude towards teacher training/ training needs:

TABLE: 6

SL/ NO	Content	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D(%)	SD(%)
1.	Both in-service & pre-service training are essential for teacher	350(70%)	150(30%)	x	x	x
2.	Pre-service TT is more essential than in- service training	250 (50%)	90(18%)	x	70(14%)	90(18%)
3.	Time period for training is sufficient	10 (2%)	320(64%)	x	130(26%)	40(8%)

Source: Field study (Questionnaire 5, 6, 7)

This table shows that 100% teachers had supported the usefulness of teachers training and agreed that both the in-service and pre-service training are essential for a teacher where as 30% respondents are agreed and 70% respondents are strongly agreed.

The table shows that 50% respondents are strongly agreed & 18% respondents are agreed that pre-service teacher training is more essential than in-service training but 14% respondents are disagreed & 18% respondents are strongly disagreed in this aspect.

The respondents have showed their opinion as both satisfaction and dissatisfaction on time period for training. 64% respondents are agreed and 2% respondents are strongly agreed with the time duration of their training period whereas 26% respondents are disagreed and 8% respondents are strongly disagreed with the time duration of their training period.

OBJECTIVE:2

Attitude towards changing the behaviour of a teacher through the training:

TABLE: 7

SL	Content	SA	A	U	D	SD
1	TT can bring changes of teacher's behaviour	330(66%)	170(34%)	x	x	x
2	TT helps to develop leadership skills	150(30%)	350(70%)	x	x	x
3	Learn new & innovative technique to be used in the classroom	335(67%)	165(33%)	x	x	x
4	Importance given to use teaching-aids in classroom	200(40%)	300(60%)	x	x	x
5	TT can Help to become a good teacher.	300(60%)	200(40%)	x	x	x

Source: Questionnaire: 8, 9, 10, 16, 18,

Table No.8, shows that 34% respondents had agreed and 66% respondents had strongly agreed that teachers training programme can bring changes in teacher's behaviour. Thus, 70% trainees had agreed and 30% trainees had strongly agreed that teacher's leadership skill can be developed through training. Again 33% respondents are agreed and 67% respondents are strongly agreed that a teacher can learn new and innovative technique in training period which should be used in the actual classroom. All the respondents had also informed that training gave importance to use the teaching-aids in the actual classroom to motivate the students. 100% respondents have said that teacher training can help to become good teacher where as 40% respondents are agreed and 60% respondents are strongly agreed.

OBJECTIVE:3

Teacher's perception about Curriculum/ Methods of teacher training prog :

TABLE: 8

SL/NO	Content	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
1.	Learn to prepare lesson plan during training period	-	500(100%)	-		-
2.	Practice the Micro-teaching & Macro-teacher during training	-	400(80%)	-	100(20%)	-
3.	Training give importance to use the teaching aids in the classroom	200(40%)	300(60%)	-		-
4.	Satisfaction with the relevance of syllabus of teacher training	180(36%)	200(40%)	-	120(24%)	-

Source: Questionnaire 11, 12, 16, 17

Table no.9 reveals that all the respondents have learnt to prepare lesson plan. But 20% respondents have informed that they have not practiced the Micro-teaching and Macro-teaching during the training period, only 80% respondents have practiced it. The table shows that 300(60%) respondents are agreed and 200(40%) respondents are strongly agreed and noted that all resource persons advised to the trainees to use teaching aids in their normal classroom. From the above table it has found that out of 500 respondents 200(40%) respondents are satisfied and 180(36%) are strongly satisfied with the relevance of syllabus or curriculum of teacher training programme but 120(24%) respondents are not satisfied with curriculum and said that most of the curriculum are theory based not practical based.

OBJECTIVE:4

Perception of BRC/CRC and Coordinators about Curriculum/ Methods/ Training Modules:

TABLE: 9

SL	Content	SA	A	U	D	SD
1	Motivate the students through teaching aids	100%	x	x	x	x
2	Motivate the teachers to use the teaching aids in their classes	x	100%		x	x
3	Satisfied with syllabus or curriculum of TT programs.	80%	10%	x	10%	
4	Give suggestions to trainee to improve their methods of teaching	100%	x	x	x	x
5	For different subjects different methods can be used	x	100%	x	x	x
6	Constant training may arise problems to complete syllabus in their classes	x	80%	x	20%	x
7	Suggestions to improve the syllabus of TT	x	100%	x	x	x

Source: Questionnaire 13,14,15,17, 18, 19, 21

The table reveals that 100% respondents (RP) has agreed that by using teaching aids teachers can motivate the student's interest. So, all RP have encouraged the teachers to use the teaching aids in their classes. But from this table it is cleared that

10% respondents are satisfied and 80% respondents are strongly satisfied with syllabus, on the other hand 10% respondents have showed their dissatisfaction on syllabus or curriculum of teacher's training. All the respondents expect a suitable syllabus which will be very useful for the trainees and due to this reason they forwarded some valuable suggestions to improve the syllabus. The table also shows that all RP advised to the trainees to improve their methods of teaching and they are all agreed that for different subject different methods can be used for more interesting the class. Thus, 80% respondents have agreed that if the teachers/RP attend the training prog constantly, they cannot complete their courses in definite period, but 20% respondents are not agreed with that.

OBJECTIVE: 5

95% respondents including RP have forwarded some suggestions for the improvement of teachers training program. All suggestions are almost same of the trainees and RPs which are discussed below:

- Time period of training should be extended.
- Practical classes should be increased.
- More computer classes should be arranged.
- Training must be related to school based curriculum.
- RPs should be more active and more and more knowledgeable and learned persons should be selected as RP.
- Audio-Visual Aids (technology) should be used in a wide manner in training classes.
- More importance should be provided on language(English) teaching.
- More emphasis should be provided to learn new techniques and methods and to give knowledge about different skills.
- RPs must use audio-visual materials to show some items like action song, recitation, writing skill, reading skill etc.

ANALYSIS OF OBSERVATION THE CLASSROOM SITUATION BY RESEARCHER:

I have visited 10 schools of Tinsukia and Doomdooma town to meet the students and to see the classroom situation that to study the changes of teachers behaviour in applying the new and innovative teaching techniques at classroom by the trainees after getting training. I have observed the situation of schools and training centers as a whole with the following components:

- Introducing of lesson
- Content deliberation
- Use of teaching aids.
- Motivation given during teaching.
- Activity based teaching etc.

I have found from my field study that the teachers are not aware of the skill 'introducing a lesson'. Teachers generally use the lecture cum explanation method in their classroom. Demonstration method is used rarely. It clears from my field study that facilities are not available to use the modern technology in their classes. Some of the teachers use teaching-aids like charts, maps, globe etc. in their classes. I have also seen some flow charts, Maps and some important points written in wall of the classrooms in all schools where I visited. Thus, the teacher tries to motivate the students.

I come to know from the teachers and students of the schools where I visited that activity and project works are given to the students time to time to know their innovative and creative thinking.

Weaknesses of Teacher Training Programme:

Some weaknesses of teacher training programme noted by respondents are discussed below:

- Most of the respondents have reported that many resource persons used mainly lecture method while communicating with trainees instead of demonstration technique. They used traditional method of instruction and dictating of notes. They have no planned and systematic awareness and control over instructional technology and no interest to use the teaching aids in the classroom.
- Most of the respondents have said that time period of training (in some cases) is not sufficient. Because all methods and skills cannot be practiced within the limited period.
- Majority of the respondents dissatisfied with the syllabus or curriculum of teacher training programme. They have said that the Syllabus of D.El.Ed is not comfortable and appropriate because it is more theoretical in nature, so that student teacher give more time to theory papers and a very less time to teaching practice and other practical activities.
- Most of the RPs reported that some trainees pay little attention during the course. Due to compulsion they attend the training.

Suggestions:

The experimenter has forwarded some suggestions which may be helpful to the improvement of teacher training programme.

- There is a need to improve the infrastructure of the training institutions & to look for qualitative teacher education. Sincere & serious efforts must be taken by the Governments & training institutions for the same.
- Syllabus of teacher training must be arranged carefully & systematically that it may be useful in their teaching life. It should be designed according to the needs of the learner. Thus, Theoretical part from the syllabus should be minimised and more importance should be given to practical work.
- Training should arranged special innovative programme on team teaching, panel discussion, project work, seminar and workshop etc. for encouragement and improvement of learning in various spheres. It will also provide opportunities to the teachers for the discussion of classroom problems and find out their solutions.
- The training centres should have some certain facilities like, libraries, important audio-visual aids, hostel facilities and laboratories etc. that the trainee could not face any type of troubles during the training period.
- Subject expert, very active, experienced and learned persons should be appointed as RP in any type of training programmes.
- Teacher training should be made compulsory at a regular interval of time. Thus, the State Government and the training centres should arrange refresher courses, workshop, short term courses regularly on different subjects to become aware of latest educational researches, educational problems and developments and up to date information on educational situations.

- Training should also be given on Stress management, personality development and educational management by psychologist, counsellors and educationists etc.
- After all, to make primary education useful and attractive, teachers should be given training in a proper way. Thus, the necessary steps should be taken by the Government for the improvement of teacher education and necessary funds will be released for the development of the training institutions. The teachers should also try to rehabilitate themselves and not confine their activities to the four walls of their schools but come out from the same and go ahead and make society good.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] AGGARWAL, J.C. Teacher and Education in a developing society. Vikas publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- [2] AGARWAL, V. P. and G. KAMLESRAO. 1997. The Quality of In-service Teacher Training Programmes for Primary School Teachers-An Appraisal Study, Teacher Empowerment and School Effectiveness at Primary Stage International Perspective, NCERT.
- [3] ANAND, C.L. 1988. Aspects of Teacher Education. S. Chand and Company Pvt. Ltd. ARORA, R. K. S. 2010. Effectiveness of Teacher Training in Quality Improvement of Elementary Education- A Study, Regional Institute of Education (NCERT), Ajmer.
- [4] BEHERA, LAXMIDHAR. 2011. Study of Impact of In-service Teacher Training under SSA on Classroom Transaction of Bihar State, Regional Institute of Education (NCERT), Bhubaneswar, Odisha.
- [5] CHAUHAN, D. R. et al. 2009. A Micro Research Study of In-service Teacher Training Programme under SSA in (Sunni) Educational Block of District Shimla, SSA Report, Shimla, Himachal Pradesh.
- [6] CHOWDHURY, SUSANTA ROY. 2014. Effectiveness of secondary school teachers in relation to their gender, age, experience and qualification. The Clarian Volume 3, number 1 (2014) pp 141-148.
- [7] LALITHAMMA, M. S. 2011. Study of Impact of In-service Teacher Training under SSA on Classroom Transaction of Tamil Nadu State, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry.

